

1 **Male ultraviolet reflectance and female mating history influence female**
2 **mate choice and male mating success in a polyandrous lizard**

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21 **Abstract**

22 Pre-copulatory female mate choice based on male ultraviolet (UV) coloration has been
23 demonstrated in several species of birds, fishes and lizards, but post-copulatory mechanisms
24 have been largely overlooked. Here, we investigated female mate preference based on male
25 UV coloration in the common lizard *Zootoca vivipara*, in which males display conspicuous
26 UV coloration on their throat. During two successive years, we staged sequential mating trials
27 between females and four different males with UV-reduced or control belly and throat
28 coloration. We recorded pre-copulatory female behavior, copulation behavior and assigned
29 paternity to all offspring. Females were more aggressive towards UV-reduced males and, in
30 one year, UV-reduced males had a lower probability of siring at least one egg (i.e. fertilization
31 success) during the last mating trials. However, in one year, copulation was shorter with
32 control males. Altogether, our results suggest that females exert subtle pre-copulatory mate
33 preference based on male UV ornaments and, conditional on the study year and female
34 mating history, some degree of post-copulatory preference for UV-control males leading to
35 differential male fertilization success. This study suggests that UV-based female mate choice
36 may be more widespread than previously thought in the animal kingdom, and emphasize the
37 importance to use a study design well adapted to the species reproductive behavior.

38

39 **Key-words:** Color signals – Female choice – Fertilization – Paternity – Post-copulatory
40 selection – Sexual selection – Ultraviolet – *Zootoca vivipara*

41

42 **Introduction**

43 Female mate choice is a major component of sexual selection that drives the evolution of
44 male exaggerated ornaments (Andersson 1994). Choosing high quality males may increase
45 female reproductive success (Andersson 1994; Kokko et al. 2003) by providing females with
46 resources increasing their survival or fecundity (direct benefits; e.g. access to good territory,
47 paternal care, protection against predators) or with alleles enhancing the viability and/or
48 attractiveness of their offspring (indirect benefits; "good genes" and "sexy sons", Kirkpatrick
49 and Ryan 1991; Andersson 1994; Johnstone 1995). Females can assess prospective males
50 using visual, acoustic or chemical signals that correlate consistently with male quality, and
51 ultimately with those direct and indirect benefits (e.g. Cooper and Vitt 1993; Welch et al.
52 1998; Darragh et al. 2017). In particular, many animal species exhibit colorful ornaments that
53 convey an honest information about male age, phenotypic condition, or genotypic quality
54 (Senar 2006; Bradbury and Vehrencamp 2011; Weaver et al. 2017).

55 Color signals can be produced by the deposition of integumentary pigments (e.g.
56 melanin and carotenoids) that selectively absorb and reflect some wavelengths of light, by
57 coherent light-scattering nanostructures (i.e. structural coloration), or by a combination of
58 both (Shawkey and D'Alba 2017). While the role of pigment-based colors in sexual selection
59 has received much scientific attention (Svensson and Wong 2011; Roulin 2016), it is more
60 recently that the potential of structural colors, such as ultraviolet, to act as sexual signals has
61 been recognized (Prum 2006; Kemp et al. 2012, 2015). Many vertebrate species bear
62 structural coloration that reflects light in the ultraviolet (UV) range (e.g. Andersson et al.
63 1998; Siebeck 2004; Ries et al. 2008; Badiane et al. 2018) and have a visual system sensitive
64 to UV light (Bowmaker 2008; Cronin and Bok 2016). We have now good evidence that UV
65 coloration can be sexually dichromatic (Hunt et al. 1998; Names et al. 2019) and act as
66 honest, condition-dependent indicator of male quality (e.g. Keyser and Hill 1999; Keyser and

67 Hill 2000; Griggio et al. 2010). Female mate choice based on male UV coloration has been
68 demonstrated in several species of birds (e.g. Hunt et al. 1999) and fishes (e.g. Kodric-Brown
69 and Johnson 2002), and in a few species of amphibians (e.g. Secondi et al. 2012) and lizards
70 (e.g. Bajer et al. 2010). Most studies investigating the effect of UV coloration on female mate
71 choice focused on pre-copulatory mechanisms while post-copulatory mechanisms remain
72 rarely tested. Only Johnsen *et al.* (1998) investigated these aspects and found that the UV
73 coloration of male bluethroats (*Luscinia s. svecica*) positively influenced social as well as
74 genetic mate choice. In fact, we still have no clear picture of the interplay between social and
75 genetic female mate choice processes based on male UV coloration.

76 Many lizard species display ultraviolet color patches that often evolve under sexual
77 selection (e.g. Thorpe and Richard 2001; Font and Molina-Borja 2004; Martin et al. 2013;
78 MacGregor et al. 2017). UV coloration in lizards seems to function as an honest indicator of
79 male quality (e.g. Whiting et al. 2006; Molnár et al. 2012; Pérez i de Lanuza et al. 2014) and
80 has been shown to influence social aggressiveness, dominance, and contest outcome during
81 male-male competition (Stapley and Whiting 2006; Bajer et al. 2011; Martin et al. 2015;
82 Names et al. 2019). For example, in European green lizards *Lacerta viridis*, UV coloration
83 signals male quality (Molnár et al. 2012, 2013), determines male fighting success (Bajer et al.
84 2011), and females prefer males with high UV reflectance (Bajer et al. 2010). Furthermore,
85 female mate choice based on male UV coloration has been shown in only two other lizard
86 species (Olsson et al. 2011; Lisboa et al. 2017). However, none of these studies tested the
87 influence of UV signaling on male mating success.

88 Here, we investigated whether male UV coloration influences behavioral mate
89 preferences of females, mating behavior and male mating success in the common lizard
90 *Zootoca vivipara*. Common lizards occupy overlapping home ranges (Massot et al. 1992) and
91 have a promiscuous mating system characterized by frequent multiple mating in both sexes

92 (Laloi et al. 2004). During the spring mating season, males actively search for mates and their
93 throat exhibit a whitish coloration that strongly reflects UV light (Martin et al. 2013;
94 Bonnaffé et al. 2018). Mating is under partial male control in common lizards (Fitze et al.
95 2005; Fitze and Le Galliard 2008), but females can also select males by resisting (or
96 accepting) mating and by sperm selection with multiple mating (Laloi et al. 2004, 2011; Fitze
97 et al. 2005; Fitze et al. 2010). During two successive years, we presented females sequentially
98 with four different males with either a control or a reduced UV reflectance on their throat and
99 belly, while controlling for other traits important for female mate choice. We quantified
100 female resistance (or acceptance) behavior as well as pairing success and copulation duration
101 to gain insights into pre-copulatory mechanisms of choice. To investigate post-copulatory
102 mechanisms and quantify male mating success, we performed paternity analyses to assign
103 offspring to males from both UV treatments. This study design allows us to test two main
104 hypotheses. First, we hypothesize that females use male UV coloration to reject or accept a
105 mating event with a male. If so, we expect females to resist more (biting more and flipping
106 their body more often to escape) mating attempts initiated by UV-reduced males compared to
107 UV-control males. Pairing success and copulation duration should also be higher for UV-
108 control than for UV-reduced males. Second, we expect that, if cryptic female choice occurs,
109 fertilization and reproductive success should be higher for UV-control males.

110 **Materials and methods**

111 *Study species*

112 The common lizard, *Zootoca vivipara*, is a small lacertid (45-70 mm) distributed across
113 Eurasia and characterized by indeterminate growth through life. In our study site, animals
114 reach sexual maturity at one or two years of age and mating takes place in May (Fitze et al.
115 2005). Females are ovoviviparous and, after 2-3 months of gestation, give birth to 1-12 eggs
116 depending on female age and body size (Massot et al. 1992). Eggs hatch within a couple of

117 minutes after oviposition and offspring are autonomous at birth. Adult males bear a whitish
118 throat and a conspicuous belly ranging from yellow to dark red, interspersed with numerous
119 black spots. Females display a duller ventral coloration ranging from cream to orange with
120 fewer black spots than males (Bauwens 1987; Cote et al. 2008). In addition, the ventral
121 coloration shows a secondary reflectance peak in the UV range, which is especially
122 pronounced on males' throat (Martin et al. 2013). UV chroma of the throat and belly
123 coloration increases with age and size in males (Bonnaffé et al. 2018).

124 *Sampling and morphometric measurements*

125 In 2012 and 2013, we captured by hand 183 adult males (85 in 2012 and 99 in 2013, 51-62
126 mm) and 52 adult females (24 in 2012 and 28 in 2013, 57-71 mm) at the Centre de Recherche
127 en Ecologie Expérimentale et Prédictive (CEREEP-Ecotron IleDeFrance, 48°17'N, 2°41'E),
128 where males and females were maintained in separate 100-m² enclosures since 2011.
129 Individuals captured in 2012 were not used in 2013, except for 3 females and 9 males which
130 participated in both years. Males were captured before their last molt at the onset of their
131 sexual activity. Females were captured 10-15 days later once they emerged from wintering.
132 Captures occurred in mid-March 2012 but early April 2013 because of annual differences in
133 weather conditions and phenology.

134 We brought the lizards to the laboratory and measured their snout-vent length (SVL; ± 1
135 mm) and body mass (± 1 mg). We found no differences in female SVL (ANOVA, $F_{1,50} = 2.00$,
136 $p = 0.16$) and body mass ($F_{1,50} = 3.14$, $p = 0.08$), nor in male body mass ($F_{1,181} = 0.38$, $p =$
137 0.54) between the two study years, but males were larger in 2012 than in 2013 (SVL: $F_{1,181} =$
138 5.25 , $p = 0.02$, $\beta = 0.72 \pm 0.32$ mm). We also obtained reflectance spectra of the throat and
139 belly (2-3 measures per location) of each male using a spectrophotometer (see Martin et al.
140 2013 for material details). We then calculated brightness (total reflectance), yellow-red hue
141 (wavelength of maximal reflectance), yellow-red saturation (difference between maximal

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142 reflectance over the range 450-700 nm and reflectance value at 450 nm divided by average
143 reflectance over the range 300-700 nm), throat UV hue (wavelength of maximal reflectance
144 between 300 nm and 400 nm) and throat UV chroma (proportion of the UV reflectance
145 relative to the total reflectance, see Martin et al. 2013 for more details). Males displayed
146 higher throat UV hue (ANOVA, $F_{1,181} = 21.83$, $p < 0.0001$, $\beta = 3.29 \pm 0.70$), and lower
147 yellow-red hue and yellow-red saturation in 2013 than in 2012 (yellow-red hue: $F_{1,181} = 7.27$,
148 $p = 0.008$, $\beta = -5.94 \pm 2.2$; yellow-red saturation: $F_{1,181} = 21.83$, $p < 0.001$, $\beta = -0.08 \pm 0.03$)
149 but had similar brightness ($F_{1,181} = 1.41$, $p = 0.24$) and throat UV chroma ($F_{1,181} = 1.14$, $p =$
150 0.29) between years.

151 We also quantified male head morphology using a digital caliper; we measured head
152 length (from tip of the nose to the head skull-vertebral column articulation), head height
153 (maximum height at the highest part posterior to orbita), head width (width at the maximum
154 lateral extent), quadrate length, and coronoid length to the nearest 0.01 mm in all but one
155 male. All measurements were highly correlated within the same individual (Spearman
156 correlation, $r > 0.33$, all $p < 0.001$) and most traits showed yearly variation in their mean
157 similar to SVL. We therefore extracted a single metric of head size by a centered and scaled
158 principal component analysis using the *dudi.pca* procedure in *Ade4* package (Chessel et al.
159 2004). The first dominant axis (PC1) explained more than 62% of the inter-individual
160 variation in head measurements and thus could be used as a head size metric. Individual
161 scores for PC1 were positively correlated with body size ($r = 0.65$, $p < 0.0001$) but not with
162 throat UV chroma ($r = -.04$, $p = 0.54$). Males had smaller head size in 2013 than in 2012 ($F_{1,$
163 $181 = 6.46$, $p = 0.01$, $\beta = -0.66 \pm 0.26$).

164 Females were housed in large plastic boxes (45×29×22 cm), in which all behavioral
165 tests took place after 5-6 days of acclimation to minimize stress. Males were housed in
166 smaller plastic boxes (18×12×12 cm) and transferred to the female's terrarium prior to each

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167 behavioral test. All terraria were layered with sand, equipped with a small water dish, two
168 hides and a black PVC plate used for basking (4×9 cm). An incandescent bulb (25 W) and
169 white light UV-B neon tubes (Reptisun 10.0 UVB, Zoomed) provided heat and light for 8
170 hours a day. Food (crickets, *Acheta domesticus*) and water were provided *ad libitum* during
171 the experiment.

172 *Color manipulation*

173 To manipulate temporarily male UV reflectance within the natural range of variation (Martin
174 et al. 2015), we used odorless UV-blocking (290-400 nm) inorganic agents (zinc oxide and
175 titan dioxide) mixed with a fat combination of petroleum jelly and liquid paraffin
176 (respectively, 6:4:50:40 for 100 g). Males of the control group were treated with the fat
177 combination and males of the UV-reduced treatment with the fat combination mixed with the
178 inorganic agents. The combination was applied on the males' ventral skin with a soft
179 paintbrush from the tip of the nose to the anal plate. To validate our protocol, we measured
180 the gular reflectance of randomly selected male lizards ($N = 7$ per group) before and after
181 application of fat (control group) or of the UV-reducing treatment (UV-reduced group). Half
182 an hour after the application, this treatment reduced UV reflectance within the natural range
183 of variation of UV chroma (see Appendix 1), and although the effect faded with time, it
184 persisted for at least two hours after application.

185 *Mate choice trials*

186 We designed sequential mating trials by pooling males into 52 quartets (24 in 2012 and 28 in
187 2013). This design mimicked the reproductive behavior of common lizards, as highly mobile
188 males likely approach resident females in a sequential manner during the mating season.
189 Males of the same quartet were matched by SVL (± 2 mm), body mass (± 600 mg) and gular
190 as well as ventral coloration. For each quartet, two lizards were randomly attributed to the
191 control group and to the UV-reduced group. We found no differences in morphology and

192 coloration between UV-control and UV-reduced individuals prior to the experiment
193 (Student's *t*-tests, all $p > 0.27$). Each male quartet was assigned to a single female according
194 to their rank for SVL, such that larger females could mate with larger males (SVL difference
195 between males and females, mean = 6.85 mm, range = 3-11). This procedure avoided size
196 mismatches so that we could focus on the role of UV coloration in mate choice, given the
197 significant assortative mating by size in the common lizard (Richard et al. 2005).

198 Each female encountered each of the four males in a random sequence of male UV
199 treatments to avoid confounding effects with female mating history. Each female was tested
200 during four consecutive days during daytime activity period (10:00-17:00 hours), at the same
201 hour of the day for all four trials. In general, each male was tested with only one female but,
202 because of difficulties with pooling similar males in quartets, 24 males participated to two
203 different quartets and were thus presented to two females (12 in 2012 and 12 in 2013). For
204 these males, at least two days separated the two mating trials to avoid effects of sperm
205 depletion. A previous study showed that male mating history did not affect male willingness
206 to mate (Kaufman, Laloï & Le Galliard, unpub. data). We thus considered the two repeats of
207 the same male as independent observations. Similarly, 3 females and 9 males participated to
208 trials both in 2012 and 2013, against different individuals each year. We also considered
209 between-years trials of the same individual as independent observations.

210 Immediately before each trial, we emptied the female's terrarium and separated it into
211 two compartments with a removable opaque wall. After treatment application, one male was
212 introduced in the compartment unoccupied by the female. During the behavioral trials, white
213 UV-enriched light was provided by two UV-B neon tubes positioned 70 cm above the ground
214 and heat was provided by two incandescent bulbs placed above each compartment. Room
215 temperature was maintained at 20-21°C. After 10 min of acclimation, one incandescent bulb
216 of 40 W was turned off, leaving only the bulb above the female's compartment turned on to

217 generate a thermal gradient, and the opaque wall was removed gently to start behavioral
218 interactions.

219 All trials were videotaped with a digital camera (Wat-902B, Watec Co., LTD, Japan)
220 until the end of the first copulation attempt if pairing was successful or until one hour in the
221 other case. Videos were analyzed later by a person blind to the experimental treatments.
222 Interactions started first by an assessment stage during which lizards remained at a distance
223 from each other observing each other. Generally, males' and females' reproductive behaviors
224 were consistent with those observed in the wild (pers. obs.), that is that the male approached
225 and attempted to bite the female at the tip of the tail. Then, after successive bites, the male
226 moved its grip up to the posterior part of the female's abdomen. Once well positioned, the
227 male wrapped itself around the female and adjoined his cloaca to the female's cloaca, which
228 marked the beginning of a "copulation" (hereafter called, pairing event). On average, pairing
229 events lasted $24:17 \pm 08:56$ min (range: 02:45 – 56:53 min). From the beginning of the
230 sequence until copulation, females resisted more or less to the males' mating attempts by
231 successive bites or flips (the female rolled violently on itself). Thus, to assess female
232 resistance to mating and pre-copulatory female mating behavior, we counted the numbers of
233 bites and the presence of female flips (binary variable, due to strong over-dispersion in the
234 number of flips; mean = 2.64 ± 12.01 , range = 0-121) from each trial. We also extracted the
235 pairing success (the presence or absence of copulation during trial) and the duration of pairing
236 when mating was successful (the duration from cloaca apposition to partners separation).

237 Females that performed flips bit males more often (Wilcoxon rank sum test, $p < 0.0001$,
238 24.8 bites versus 5.77) and males that did not mate were more often bitten by the female ($p =$
239 0.0001 , 17 bites versus 6.54). The number of female bites was not related to the duration of
240 copulation (Spearman's rank correlation, $\rho = 0.08$, $p = 0.33$). Two days after the last
241 behavioral trial of the male, we collected a small part of their tail tip (1 mm) to extract DNA

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242 and assess paternity. Tissue samples were stored in 70% ethanol in a freezer before releasing
243 males in outdoor enclosures. Once all trials were completed, females were released in small
244 outdoor mesocosms (1 m², two females) protected from predators in order to facilitate their
245 monitoring throughout gestation. During gestation, females were provided with food and
246 water *ad libitum*.

247 *Paternity assignments*

248 We recaptured the females a few days before parturition and placed them in the same
249 laboratory conditions as before (see above). At the time of parturition, we counted the number
250 of live newborns, dead newborns, and aborted or unfertilized eggs of each clutch. Tissue
251 samples (tail tips or egg samples) were collected from all newborns and eggs as well as from
252 mothers and were stored in 70% ethanol. Females were then released in the outdoor
253 enclosures with their live newborns. Genomic DNA was extracted from all tissue samples
254 using the QIAquick 96 Purification Kit (QIAGEN) according to the manufacturer's
255 instructions. Individuals were genotyped using 5 microsatellite markers (Lv-3-19, Lv-4-72,
256 Lv-4-alpha, Lv-4-X, and Lv-4-115, Richard *et al.*, 2009). Samples were run on an ABI 3100
257 genetic analyzer (Applied Biosystems) with a Genescan 600 Liz size standard. Sample data
258 were analyzed using either Genemapper 4.1 or Strand (Toonen and Hughes 2001,
259 <http://www.vgl.ucdavis.edu/STRand>). We checked for perfect match between reproductive
260 items (newborns and eggs) and their mother, and then assessed paternities (no mismatch
261 between potential father and the reproductive item) using CERVUS (Kalinowski et al. 2007).
262 Two females did not mate during the behavioral trials. Genomic DNA could be extracted for
263 all items except for one juvenile and 10 potentially unfertilized eggs laid by six females.
264 During paternity assignment tests, we found a single candidate father for all except 2
265 juveniles and 3 dead embryos for which no valid DNA profile was available. All analyses

266 were therefore performed on a total of 230 eggs and offspring successfully attributed to a
267 unique father.

268 *Statistical analyses*

269 We used R 3.4.4 software (R Development Core Team 2017) to conduct all statistical
270 analyses. We first tested the effects of male UV treatment, study year, and trial order on the
271 behavior of females (N = 4 measures per female). To do so, we used linear mixed-effects
272 models that account for random intercept variation among females in the *lme4* (Bates et al.
273 2015) and *nlme* packages (Pinheiro et al. 2019). Generalized mixed-effects models (GLMM)
274 were implemented to analyze the number of bites (Poisson distribution, log link) and the
275 presence of flips and the pairing success (binomial distribution, logit link) using the *glmer*
276 procedure. A linear mixed-effects model (LMM) was used to analyze the duration of
277 copulation using the *lme* procedure. All initial, full models included fixed, additive effects of
278 year, trial order (categorical factor), male UV treatment as well as their two-way and three-
279 way interactions. In addition, female body size (SVLf) and male head size (PC1) were
280 included as covariates. Model assumptions were checked prior to model selection, using tests
281 of goodness-of-fit (GLMM) and residual homoscedasticity and normality (LMM). To fulfil
282 the goodness-of-fit test, we calculated a transformed aggression score by binning the range of
283 number of female bites in 20 equally spaced breaks (similar results were obtained with 15-25
284 bins). Model parameters were estimated with a maximum likelihood approach and non-
285 significant effects were tested using likelihood ratio tests (Bolker et al. 2009). Whenever test
286 statistics were borderline, we confirmed the strength of the effect by a parametric bootstrap
287 procedure of nested models ($n=1,000$ simulations) using the *PBmodcom* procedure
288 implemented in the *pblrtest* package (Halekoh and Højsgaard 2014). For the number of
289 female bites, we performed post-hoc Tukey tests to assess differences among the four trials.

290 Using generalized linear models, we further analyzed effects of male UV treatment,
291 study year, and trial order on male mating success including the proportion of fertilized eggs
292 (i.e., fertilization success) and the total number of viable offspring sired by the same male
293 (hereafter referred to as total fitness). For fertilization success, we analyzed the probability to
294 sire at least one egg instead of the proportion of fertilized eggs because this variable
295 conformed better to a binomial distribution. Results were qualitatively similar in both cases
296 however. To analyze fertilization success, we used a logistic regression (logit link, binomial
297 errors) with the *glm* procedure (Venable and Ripley 2002). Because of an excess of zero, we
298 analyzed the total male fitness using a zero-inflated model with the *zeroinfl* procedure from
299 the *pscl* package (Zeileis et al. 2008). This procedure allows fitting a two-component mixture
300 model combining a point mass at zero with a binary modelling of unobserved state (zero vs.
301 count, logit link and binomial errors) and a Poisson distribution (log link, Poisson errors). For
302 fertilization success, the initial model further included additive effects of the number of males
303 that mated with the female and the female's clutch size, and trial order was replaced by male
304 mating rank. The male mating rank excludes records for which males did not mate and
305 therefore describes better post-copulatory mechanisms than trial order. Goodness-of-fit tests
306 revealed that all initial models fitted adequately the data. All minimum adequate models were
307 then obtained by backward elimination of non-significant terms. Estimates (hereafter named
308 β) are provided with standard errors unless otherwise stated.

309 *Ethical note*

310 All procedures comply with all laws on animal experimentation in France and Europe, and
311 were approved by authorization Ce5/2011/024.

312 **Results**

313 *Female resistance behavior prior to pairing*

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314 The number of female bites ranged from 0 to 76 (mean = 9.7 ± 14.4 SD) and was best
315 predicted by the female mating history (trial order, likelihood ratio test: $df = 3, \chi^2 = 167.03, p$
316 < 0.0001), male UV treatment ($df = 1, \chi^2 = 4.48, p = 0.03$; parametric bootstrap test, $p =$
317 0.047), and study year ($df = 1, \chi^2 = 4.16, p = 0.04$). Male head size also had near-significant
318 positive effects ($df = 1, \chi^2 = 3.59, p = 0.06, \beta = 0.11 \pm 0.06$). Females were less aggressive
319 during the two first trials and bit on average about four times more during the two last trials
320 (Figure 1A). Post-hoc Tukey tests on trial order revealed that female bit more during the
321 fourth trial than any other trial ($p < 0.01$ for each pairwise comparison), and more during the
322 third trial than during the two first ($p < 0.01$ for each pairwise comparison), but there was no
323 difference between the two first trials ($p = 0.97$). In addition, females significantly bit more in
324 2013 than in 2012 ($\beta = 0.32 \pm 0.15$) and UV-reduced males received more bites than control
325 males on average ($\beta = 0.17 \pm 0.07$; control = 8.9 ± 1.20 , UV-reduced = 10.5 ± 1.61 ; Figure
326 1B). The occurrence of female flips was not influenced by male UV treatment ($df = 1, \chi^2 =$
327 $0.50, p = 0.48$) and male head size ($df = 1, \chi^2 = 0.23, p = 0.63$). Occurrence of female flips
328 increased dramatically during the fourth mating trial ($df = 3, \chi^2 = 20.41, p = 0.01$, Figure 1C)
329 and was slightly higher in 2013 than in 2012 ($df = 1, \chi^2 = 4.24, p = 0.04, \beta = 0.91 \pm 0.44$).

330 *Pairing behavior*

331 During the behavioral trials, 2 females did not mate with any males (4 %), 3 females mated
332 with only one male (5 %), 11 females with two males (21 %), 24 females with three males (47
333 %) and 12 females with four males (23 %). In addition, 45 females mated during the first trial
334 (87%), 44 during the second (85%), 34 during the third (65%), and 22 during the fourth trial
335 (42%). Pairing success was influenced by trial order ($df = 3, \chi^2 = 29.6, p < 0.01$, Figure 2A)
336 and tended to be higher in 2013 than in 2012 ($df = 1, \chi^2 = 3.53, p = 0.06, 2013: \beta = 0.74 \pm$
337 0.40). Pairing occurred on average in more than 80% of the pairs interactions during the first
338 and the second behavioral trials, but this dropped down to ca. 70% during the third trial and to

339 ca. 40% during the fourth trial. Pairing success was not influenced by male UV treatment (df
 340 = 1, $\chi^2 = 1.41$, $p = 0.23$, Figure 2) but increased slightly with male head size ($df = 1$, $\chi^2 = 3.83$,
 341 $p = 0.05$, $\beta = 0.39 \pm 0.20$). When pairing was successful ($N = 141$), the duration of copulation
 342 (mean = 1444 sec \pm 510 SD, range = 121-2881 sec) was not predicted by trial order ($F_{3,87} =$
 343 0.68, $p = 0.56$) nor male head size ($F_{1,89} = 0.93$, $p = 0.30$). Instead, copulation duration was
 344 influenced by the two-way interaction between study year and male UV treatment ($F_{1,89} =$
 345 6.73, $p = 0.01$). In 2012, there was no effect of male UV treatment on copulation duration ($\beta =$
 346 -160 sec \pm 126.3, $t = -1.27$, $p = 0.21$), but a drastic drop in copulation duration of UV-control
 347 males occurred in 2013. As a result, copulation was 25% shorter for UV-control males than
 348 for UV-reduced males in 2013 ($\beta = 431$ sec \pm 166.2, $t = 2.6$, $p = 0.01$, Figure 2B).

349 *Male mating success*

350 Paternity assignment tests showed that, among females paired with at least one male ($N = 50$),
 351 8 did not produce any egg (16 %), 1 produced one egg (2 %), 14 produced from 2 to 4 eggs
 352 (29 %), and 27 females produced from 5 to 8 eggs (53 %). Mated females that did not produce
 353 any egg most probably failed to ovulate because they did not significantly increase body mass
 354 (pers. obs.). Clutch size was not correlated with female body size (Pearson's product-moment
 355 correlation test, $r = 0.06$, $p = 0.68$). Among the 47 females paired with at least two males, 12
 356 females (25 %) were polyandrous and one clutch was sired by three different males.

357 The probability to sire at least one egg (our estimate of fertilization success) was best
 358 predicted by a three-way interaction between study year, male mating rank and male UV
 359 treatment (binomial regression, $df = 3$, $\chi^2 = 10.3$, $p = 0.02$) and by the number of mating ($df =$
 360 1, $\chi^2 = 4.27$, $p = 0.04$, negative effect), but not by male head size ($df = 1$, $\chi^2 = 0.91$, $p = 0.34$),
 361 male throat UV coloration ($df = 1$, $\chi^2 = 0.17$, $p = 0.68$) or total clutch size ($df = 1$, $\chi^2 = 0.49$, p
 362 = 0.48). Controlling for a positive effect of copulation duration on fertilization success ($df = 1$,
 363 $\chi^2 = 15.4$ $p < 0.001$, $\beta = 0.99 \pm 0.29$) further improved the statistical significance of the three-

364 way interaction ($df = 3, \chi^2 = 11.5, p = 0.01$). Analysis of data from 2012 showed no effect of
365 male UV treatment and male mating rank on fertilization success (all $p > 0.25$): each male
366 fertilized on average 21.3 % of females' eggs. In 2013, fertilization success was affected by
367 the interaction between male mating rank and male UV treatment ($df = 3, \chi^2 = 15.75, p <$
368 0.01). Male fertilization success was similar for both UV-reduced and control males during
369 the first and second mating, but it dropped to zero during the third and fourth mating for UV-
370 reduced males (Figure 3).

371 We found no effect of the UV treatment and design factors on total male fitness (for
372 zero excess, effects of year: $df = 1, \chi^2 = 3.20, p = 0.07$; trial order: $df = 3, \chi^2 = 4.25, p = 0.23$;
373 male UV treatment: $df = 1, \chi^2 = 0.48, p = 0.49$; for count data, effects of year: $df = 1, \chi^2 =$
374 $0.21, p = 0.64$; trial order: $df = 3, \chi^2 = 0.88, p = 0.83$; male UV treatment: $df = 1, \chi^2 = 1.15, p =$
375 0.28). Male total fitness was not influenced by throat UV coloration (all $p > 0.16$), but it
376 increased with male head size (zero excess: $\chi^2 = 0.41, p = 0.52$, count: $\chi^2 = 7.01, p = 0.01, \beta =$
377 0.21 ± 0.08).

378 **Discussion**

379 Our study provides evidence suggesting that females can exert subtle mate preference (as
380 defined in Edward 2015) with respect to male UV coloration in common lizards. The effects
381 of male UV coloration on precopulatory mate preference, copulation duration and male
382 fertilization success were modulated by the female's mating history and the study year, and
383 did not lead to significant changes in male total fitness. Specifically, we found evidence that
384 females were biting UV-reduced males, males of the last two trials, and males presented in
385 2013 significantly more. As a result, pairing success decreased with females' mating history.
386 Thus, these results seem to indicate that female limit their number of sexual partners, which
387 supports the hypothesis that mating is costly for female common lizards (Fitze et al. 2005;
388 White et al. 2011).

389 *Pre-copulatory and copulatory behavior*

390 In line with our expectations, females were significantly more aggressive towards UV-
391 reduced males than towards control males, and were also more aggressive during the second
392 year of the study and during the last two mating trials. This suggests that females were more
393 “reluctant” to mate with UV-reduced males in general (e.g. Laloï et al. 2011), and with later
394 presented males. In addition, females were least aggressive towards their first mates, maybe to
395 ensure fertilization of their eggs, and became more aggressive towards the subsequent
396 partners, which supports the hypothesis of trading-up mate choice in common lizards
397 (Jennions and Petrie 2000; Fitze et al. 2010; Laloï et al. 2011).

398 During the second year of the study, females mated for shorter time with UV-control
399 males than UV-reduced males. This result is counter-intuitive since longer pairing is
400 associated with larger amount of inseminated sperm, which increases male mating success
401 (reviewed in Simmons 2005). We are left with speculations to explain this pattern that runs
402 counter our expectations. Perhaps females perceived UV-control males as potentially more
403 harmful, and shortening copulations with those males allow females to gain direct benefits.
404 While UV features have been shown to correlated with bite force in wall lizards (Pérez i de
405 Lanuza et al. 2014), it does not seem to be the case in *Z. vivipara*. Instead, UV features appear
406 to correlate with male body size and sprint speed (Bonnaffé et al. 2018; unpublished results).
407 Given the randomized experimental design, it is unlikely that the observed differences are due
408 to differences in other communication channels, which may have interfered with the UV
409 treatment.

410 Interestingly, year of study appears to be an important factor explaining our results.
411 Females were more aggressive and tried to escape more in 2013 than in 2012, and copulation
412 duration decreased in 2013 for UV-control males. These effects could have to do with the
413 males being smaller in 2013 than in 2012, making it easier for females to reject them although

414 our analyses controlled for differences in males head size. Other year-dependent factors may
415 also have contributed such as yearly climate variations in the enclosures leading to differences
416 in reproductive timing, female condition and/or receptivity.

417 Our results add to a growing list of studies showing that male UV coloration can
418 influence some components of female pre-copulatory mate choice in many species of birds
419 (Bennett et al. 1996, 1997; Andersson and Amundsen 1997; Hunt et al. 1999; Siitari et al.
420 2002; Pearn et al. 2003; Zampiga et al. 2008; Leitão et al. 2014) , fishes (Kodric-Brown and
421 Johnson 2002; Macías Garcia and De Perera 2002; Smith et al. 2002; Cummings et al. 2003,
422 2006; Boulcott et al. 2005; Rick et al. 2006) and in one species of amphibians (Secondi et al.
423 2012). As emphasized earlier, this is the fourth lizard species in which it has been suggested
424 that female mate choice is based on male UV coloration (Bajer et al. 2010; Olsson et al. 2011;
425 Lisboa et al. 2017). Several studies failed to find conclusive effects of male UV coloration on
426 female mate choice (Hunt et al. 2001; Ballentine and Hill 2003; Cummings et al. 2003; Liu et
427 al. 2007; Kurvers et al. 2010). It could indeed be simply because UV-based female mate
428 choice is absent in these cases, or because the methodology used was not adequate to detect
429 its presence. First of all, as pointed out by Andersson and Amundsen (1997), Siitari *et al.*
430 (2002) and Kurvers *et al.*, (2010), several mate choice experiments completely removed or
431 reduced male UV reflectance outside the natural range and thus, animals looked ‘odd’. A
432 better approach is to manipulate UV reflectance within the natural range as we did here, and
433 enhancing UV reflectance may provide additional support. UV-based mate choice is perhaps
434 more widespread than previously thought in lizards, and in vertebrates in general.

435 Furthermore, most experiments assessed female mate choice using simultaneous
436 choice tests. A simultaneous mate choice design consists in presenting simultaneously two or
437 more males, placed in individual boxes such that they do not see each other, to a female from
438 which they are separated by a thin filter. Such a design controls well for male-male

439 interactions but interferes with physical and chemical exchanges usually involved in mate
440 selection (Shackleton et al. 2005). Yet, reproductive success of males is modulated by their
441 ability to control the mating behavioral process, especially in the context of sexual conflict
442 (Arnqvist and Rowe 2005), to which a simultaneous mate choice design is blind. In addition,
443 these study designs can only detect mate choice when females actively choose one male over
444 another, but fail to identify more subtle mate choice processes such as female resistance to
445 mating, and do not address copulatory and post-copulatory selective processes (Eberhard
446 1996). Here, the UV manipulation affected female pre-copulatory and copulation behaviors
447 but not pairing success, perhaps because the outcome of female-male interactions was to some
448 extent under male control (Fitze et al. 2005; Fitze and Le Galliard 2008). Moreover,
449 sequential mate choice is likely to be the norm for many polyandrous species in which
450 females can rarely compare males simultaneously (Milinski and Bakker 1992). We thus
451 recommend a similar design with direct physical interaction for future investigations of
452 female mate choice based on male ornaments in species in which mating occurs sequentially
453 in nature.

454 *Effects of the UV manipulation on male mating success*

455 First of all, we found that only 12 females (25 %) were polyandrous and only one clutch was
456 sired by three different males. This is a relatively low degree of polyandry compared to
457 previous studies (e.g. Fitze et al. 2005). Paternity analyses revealed that UV-reduced and
458 control males had similar fertilization success in the first year of study despite increased
459 female aggression towards UV-reduced males. In the second year of study, however, we
460 found that fertilization success was similar for both UV-reduced and control males when they
461 were the first or second mating partners of females, but it was much smaller for UV-reduced
462 males when they were one of the two last mating partners. This suggests that some form of
463 cryptic female preference (Eberhard 1996) or differential allocation (Sheldon 2000) based on

464 male UV coloration negatively skewed fertilization success of UV-reduced males in the
465 second year. In other words, females may be able to modulate, at least to some extent, the
466 fertilization process. For example, they may use differential allocation based on male UV
467 coloration; females would allocate more resources when they mate with UV-control males
468 because they appear as more attractive than UV-reduced males.

469 However, we found that male UV treatment did not relate to male total fitness, which
470 included all pre-copulatory and post-copulatory components of sexual selection, whereas
471 there was a slight positive effect of head size. It should be noted that our study design was not
472 well-suited to test for fitness differences among males, as only one female was presented to
473 each male, and males and females were size-matched. In these conditions, the effect of male
474 perceived or intrinsic quality on male total fitness depended largely on female clutch size.
475 When we included female clutch size in these models, it was the only significant explanatory
476 variable, masking the effect of head size (Appendix 2).

477 *Conclusion*

478 In summary, our study suggests that male UV coloration acts as visual signal on which
479 females rely before and at least to some extent after copulation. However, the role of UV
480 coloration was not consistent across study years and trial order, indicating that female mate
481 preference is complex and probably involves other parameters. Overall, this supports the idea
482 that male UV coloration indicates some aspects of male quality in this species. In addition,
483 our results suggest that females may be able to bias sperm use in favor of males with higher
484 UV reflectance. Finally, we advocate that adequate study design may reveal that UV-based
485 female mate preference is actually more widespread than previously thought in lizards, and in
486 polyandrous species in general.

487

488 **Research data**

489 The data used in this study will be made freely available on a public repository upon
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491

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737 **Figures legends**

738 **Figure 1.** Pre-mating behavioural responses of females to the manipulation of the male UV
739 throat coloration. Number of bites performed by females against males during each
740 behavioural trial increased in response to changes in trial order (A, from 1st to fourth
741 behavioural trial) and with experimental reduction of throat UV coloration (B). The
742 occurrence of female flip behaviour increased during the last trial order independently from
743 the male UV treatment (C). Raw data are represented as means \pm SE.

744

745 **Figure 2.** Pairing success and duration in females according to the manipulation of the male
746 UV throat coloration. The pairing success decreased in response to changes in trial order
747 (from 1st to fourth behavioural trial) irrespective of male UV treatment (A). Pairing duration,
748 a good potential indicator of copulation duration, was influenced by experimental reduction of
749 male UV reflectance differently in 2012 (no significant effect) and in 2013 (significant
750 effect). Raw data are given as means \pm SE.

751

752 **Figure 3.** Proportion of fertilised eggs by males in 2012 and 2013 depending on their order of
753 presentation to females and their UV treatment. Data are given as means (\pm SE). Note that
754 fertilisation success was quantified by the probability to sire at least one egg (see main text)
755 but results were qualitatively similar if we examined the proportion of fertilised eggs.

756

757 **Figure 1**

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761 **Figure 2**

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767 **Figure 3**

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Female mate choice for UV reflectance

769 **Appendix 1.** Experimental manipulation of throat coloration. Mean throat reflectance (\pm SE)
770 of male common lizards from a control group treated with a fat cream (upper) and a UV-
771 reduced group treated with a UV reducing cream (lower), before and 30 min after application
772 (N=7 per group). After 30 min, the control did not change spectral parameters while the UV
773 reducing treatment significantly shifted the maximal peak of UV reflectance up 4.35 ± 2.86
774 nm towards the visible domain and reduced UV chroma by 4.54 ± 1.69 % without changing
775 the other spectral parameters (Martin *et al.*, 2015).
776

779 **Appendix 2.** Our results showed that male fertilisation success, but not male total fitness, was
780 influenced by our UV signal manipulations. Because the males mated with only one female,
781 we would have expected male total fitness to reflect female clutch size. We therefore added
782 the variable “female clutch size” to the generalised linear models fitted on male total fitness.
783 As expected, female clutch size was the only main predictor of female clutch size (zero
784 excess: $p = 0.02$, $\beta = -0.19 \pm 0.058$; count:, $p < 0.01$, $\beta = 0.21 \pm 0.05$) and masked the effect of
785 male head size.

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